

Pin Worm Infestation: An Uncommon Presentation as Recurrent Urinary Tract Infection in Adult: A Case ReportShradhanjali Pani¹, Taranisen Sethi², Pratyush Kumar Panda³, Panchanan Sethi⁴¹Assistant Professor, Department of General Medicine, VIMSAR, Burla²Assistant Professor, Department of General Medicine, VIMSAR, Burla³Postgraduate, Department of General Medicine, VIMSAR, Burla⁴Asst. Surgeon, CHC Jagannathprasad, Ganjam

Received: 05-08-2024 / Revised: 23-08-2024 / Accepted: 02-09-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Taranisen Sethi

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Pin worm (*Enterobius vermicularis*) is common intestinal nematode infection in India and with a disproportionate number of cases among children. Mostly they affect gastrointestinal tract. Genital enterobiasis rarely occur and chronic infection of urinary tract even rarer. At night, adult female pin worm migrates to perianal area and after laying egg goes to genital tract due to proximity of anal canal in female patients. Here we report a case of 26-year-old female presented with urinary frequency, dysuria, lower abdominal pain, and adult motile pin worm identified on urine sample.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Enterobiasis is relatively benign condition having worldwide distribution. Humans are the only hosts and infection occurs by accidental ingestion of infective stages. Occasionally, ectopic infections occur in the genital organs or urinary tract of females with chronic pelvic peritonitis and ileocolitis also reported [1]. Genital enterobiasis is found in several country although with low prevalence. There are number of cases like 37-years-old Korean women with *E. vermicularis* ova in vaginal smear [2], 35-years-old with enterobiasis and cervical carcinoma [3], 40-years-old Indian women with vaginal enterobiasis [4] and endometrial endometriosis in a 40-years-old Chinese woman [5]. Out of which chronic urinary tract infection is even a rare entity, only one case reported by Singh et al [6].

Case presentation:

A 26-year-old female presented with complain of 10 days history of burning micturition, lower abdominal pain, urinary frequency. There is history of similar symptoms 1 month back and diagnosed to be urinary tract infection with presence of pus cell in urine examination that subsided with some medications. Patient also noticed passing of 2-3 white colour worm like structures at a time during urination (3 times in last 2 months). General as well as systemic examination was normal. Complete blood count test was normal. On Urinalysis, pyuria present without bacteriuria. Urine culture was sterile. However, on second visit, patient brought urine sample containing worm, which was small white motile worm of size 12mm on low power microscope and identified as mature female *Enterobius vermicularis* (Figure 1).

Figure 1

Stool examination was normal without having egg. Ultrasound examination was normal with normal kidney size and urinary bladder. She was prescribed with 2 doses of Tab albendazole (400 mg) at an interval of 2 weeks. Symptoms got resolved and repeat urinalysis was normal after 6 weeks.

Discussion

Enterobius vermicularis is a highly contagious helminth infection. It especially affects children, and having ubiquitous geographic distribution. Adult *E. vermicularis* are white and small with transversely striated skin. The Female (9-12 mm) having a long pointed tail and vulva in anterior part of body, while male (2.5 mm) has blunt and posteriorly curved extremity. They are transmitted either directly from anal/perianal region to mouth by fingernail contamination or exposure of viable eggs on contaminated objects or thirdly via retroinfection through migration of eggs from anal mucosa up to the bowel. Pin worm commonly affects large intestine and terminal ileum and results in minute ulcerations at the attachment site. However, extraintestinal manifestation can also occur affecting female genital tract, liver, lung, ovary, spleen, kidney and appendix [7]. The mature female migrates down to anus when the ovary is full of eggs and then emerge out to lay egg on perianal skin. In our case, adult worm may migrate from perianal area to genital orifices to urinary bladder through urethra causing cystitis and urethritis [8]. During the process some coliform bacteria migrates from colon and rectum to urinary bladder and start to multiply.

General symptoms vary from mild itching to pain which occurs mainly at night. Scratching of perianal region results in secondary infection. Vulvitis may occur leading to mucoid discharge. Diagnosis is made by identification of adult worm or eggs in perianal scrapings (scotch tape and Sellotape swab method), faeces or swabs from under the fingernails or by finding of adult worms around the anus.

Intestinal and genital enterobiasis is successfully treated with albendazole, pyrantel pamoate or mebendazole usually 2 doses in an interval of 2 weeks.

Conclusion

Enterobius vermicularis is a ubiquitous nematodes affecting humans. However, it is a rare cause of recurrent UTI but can lead to diagnostic uncertainty and need high degree of suspicion. Although temporary cure is simple, eradication may be difficult. Therefore, retreatment along with proper hygiene maintenance is necessary.

Conflict of Interest: No

References

1. Macdeo T, MacCarty RL. Eosinophilic ileocolitis secondary to enterobius vermicularis; a case report. *Abdom Imaging* 2000;25:530-12.
2. Kim SCE, Lee YHH, Ko WLS, et al. Enterobius vermicularis Ova in a Vaginal Smear. *Korean J Pathol.* 2010; 44:341-342.
3. Raju K, Verappa S, Murthy S. Enterobius vermicularis infestation masquerading as cervical carcinoma: A cytological diagnosis. *J Nat Sci Biol Med.* 2015;6(2):476-479.
4. Shetty J, Kulkarni D, Prabhu V. Eggs containing larvae of Enterobius vermicularis in vaginal smear. *J Cytol.* 2012;29(1):94-96.
5. Ying WN, Bian N. Enterobius Vermicularis Infestation of the Endometrium—A Cause of Menstrual Irregularity and Review of Literature. *Ann Acad Med.* 2011;40(11):514-515.
6. Singh S and Samantaray JC. Topical anthelmintic treatment of recurrent genitourinary enterobiasis. *Genitourin Med* 1989; 65: 284-285.
7. Ying Woo Ng, Siok Bian Ng, Jeffrey JH Low. Enterobius Vermicularis Infestation of the Endometrium – A Cause of Menstrual Irregularity and Review of Literature. *Aust. J. Gynae. & Obstet.* 2011; 40:11.
8. Serpytis M, Seinins D. Fatal case of ectopic enterobiasis: Enterobius vermicularis in the kidneys. *Scand. J. Urol. Nephrol.* 2012;46(1):70-2.